
MANAGERIAL PRACTICES ADOPTED BY PRINCIPALS FOR IMPROVING TEACHERS' JOB PERFORMANCE IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE

Dr. Martha Chioma Ibezim

Department of Educational Management and Policy
Faculty of Education,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka

Abstract

The study investigated managerial practices adopted by principals for improving teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study comprised 7,293 respondents made up of 266 principals and 7,027 teachers in the 266 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The sample for this study consisted of 809 respondents made up of 106 principals and 703 teachers drawn using proportionate stratified random sampling technique. The researcher-developed instrument namely: "Managerial Practices for Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (MPTJPO) was used for data collection. The instrument was subjected to face validation by three experts made up of three experts from Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. The internal consistency of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha method which yielded coefficient values of 0.81 and 0.79 for Clusters A and B of the instrument respectively with overall coefficient value of 0.80. The instrument was administered by the researcher and five research assistants and 97% return rate was recorded. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and t-test was used to test hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed among others that participatory decision-making and teamwork practices are adopted by principals for improving teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. It was also found that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the participatory decision-making and teamwork practices adopted by principals for improving teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that principals should undertake leadership courses to augment the skills and knowledge of participatory decision-making practices for improving the job performance of teachers.

Keywords: Managerial Practices, Principals, Teachers, Job Performance, Teamwork, Decision-making

Introduction

Education is a veritable tool for transmitting knowledge, equipping skills and shaping attitudes of individuals to enable them make substantial contributions towards the progress of the society. It is also recognized all over the world as the bedrock for fostering development by emancipating individuals from poverty, unemployment, hunger and illiteracy. Ngurukwem, Adebola and Ugwoegbu (2024) opined that education is a key to unlocking potentials, inculcating values and building the character of individuals. Learners receive education at basic level before proceeding to secondary schools.

Secondary education is further training and learning opportunities which is available for students immediately after the basic school level to acquire desirable knowledge and skills for higher studies and meaningful contributions towards the development of the society. Ibezim and Ikediugwu (2023) pointed out that secondary education is the intermediary between the primary and tertiary levels of education which train and supply middle-level manpower required for the development of the society. Also, Egboka and Onyeagba (2024) argued that secondary school is a post-primary learning institution that grooms students with crucial skills and impart them with knowledge for self-reliance, useful living and furtherance of formal education in higher institution. The daily affairs of every secondary school are coordinated and managed by a principal.

Principal is the leader, director, coordinator and manager of a secondary school. Orunbon, Isaac-Philips and Onyene (2024) described principal as a person who plays a pivotal role in providing leadership and guidance to teachers to improve learning outcomes in a secondary school. The principal is the chief administrator saddled with the responsibility of ensuring that teachers are organized, controlled and motivated to carry out their duties to achieve expected results in a secondary school. Principal is described by Nwankwo and Edeani (2023) as the most senior members of the teaching staff that is appointed to pilot and coordinate the daily affairs of a secondary school. Principal is the administrative head who is charged with the greatest responsibility of managing the daily affairs and resource of a secondary school. Ikediugwu and Ibezim (2023) described principal as chief executive officer saddled with the responsibility of ensuring smooth running of the daily programmes of a secondary school. The principal can ensure smooth functioning of a secondary school through engaging some managerial practices.

Managerial practices are the techniques for that regulating behaviour and coordinating activities to ensure that daily programmes run smoothly in secondary schools. Managerial practices according to Edo and Johnson (2024), are strategies put forward by managers to govern the actions of members of staff for effective administration of secondary schools. Several scholars have highlighted different dimensions of managerial practices. Asuquo and Etor (2021) highlighted different management practices that abound in educational organizations as follow: communication, motivation and participatory decision-making practices. In the same vein, Aropet al (2020) listed managerial practices as follow: motivation, discipline, records management, school supervision, conflict management and communication. Also, Edo and Johnson (2024) outlined managerial practices to include teamwork, strategic planning and participatory decision-making practices. This study focused on participatory decision-making and team dimensions of managerial practices.

Decision-making is the act of choosing the most preferred courses of action among many options of solving problems to achieve set objectives. Ayeni (2018) posited that decision making begins with identifying a problem, mapping out activities and

implementation strategies in needed time. The principals require the inputs of other members of staff in the processes of making decisions. Participatory decision-making practice is concerned with the involvement of staff in the process of choosing most suitable course of actions required to solve problems in an organization. Ayeni and Ojo (2022) posited that participatory decision-making is a process whereby principals seek opinions, ideas, and suggestions of teachers and consider them in deciding final course of action in secondary schools. Teachers who are provided with opportunities to make inputs of school affairs are more likely to accept and implement final decisions made by principals in secondary schools. Ebunu (2022) noted that teachers are closer to students to have significant information that can inform good suggestions on better ways of doing their work effectively. Participatory decision-making process is necessary for building atmosphere of trust and culture of teamwork in secondary schools.

Teamwork is the act of bringing people together to jointly and harmoniously carry out a specific task for attainment of common goal. Ughamadu, Ezeaku and Nwogbo (2024) noted that teamwork is a condition where two or more staff who are interdependent in a given task, communicate, cooperate and interact effectively to accomplish the task. Furthermore, they pointed out that teachers who work as a team display high levels of cooperation, show mutual support and give each other constructive feedback for continual improvement of instructional activities. Amaefule, Michael and Umeh (2024) posited that teamwork cultivates a supportive and collaborative school environment characterized by continuous learning, shared responsibility and innovation. Teamwork practices are coordinated efforts of creating synergy in performing tasks among members of staff. Nnaemego and Ikediugwu (2020) noted that teamwork create a quality work environment that encourages strong staff commitment to continuous improvement of the school system. Teamwork practices enable members of staff to put collective efforts towards executing a given task to improve their job performance

Teachers' job performance is the outcome of official tasks executed by members of teaching staff at a given time. Teachers' job performance is defined by Nwankwo and Edeani (2023), as the measure of the degree and ability of teaching staff to carry out their duties diligently to achieve predetermined goals. It is act of carryout work activities to meet the demand of a job in a given period. Amaefule, Michael and Umeh (2024) described teachers' job performance as the responsibilities and actions carried out by staff teaching staff to achieve daily classroom objectives and broader educational goals. Teachers' job performance is described by Oyewole, Ola-Ogundele, Bamikole (2020), as the duties performed by teaching staff at a particular period in the school system in achieving organizational goals. The job performance of teachers could be assessed through the work activities such as lesson preparation, utilization of instructional resources, classroom organization, instructional delivery, conducting of examination and preparation of results among others.

The nonchalant attitude and unacceptable behaviours displayed by some secondary school teachers in Anambra State may be attributed to lapses in managerial practices of principals. The teachers tend to be irregular in school for teaching the students, comelateness to school, exhibit poor self-discipline, fail to complete scheme of work/dairy and exhibit other forms of professional misconducts in public secondary schools in Anambra State. To buttress this, Obi and Chukwudebelu (2024) observed lateness to duty, non-coverage of scheme of work, truancy, poor record keeping, irregular attendance to classes among secondary school teachers in Anambra State. Ezewuzie and Eziamaka (2018) noted that most of the decisions were taken by some principals without consultations with their teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Also, Egboka and Onyeagb (2024) noted that teachers were denied the opportunities to access vital information and air their views during

decisions making process in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Amaefule, Michael and Umeh (2024) observed that there is limited collaborative environment which make teachers struggle to work together cohesively, share best practices, or collectively address challenges in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Also, Ihueze and Unachukwu (2020) noted that most principals isolate teachers from important administrative functions thereby telling them to wait for their own turn in public secondary schools in Anambra State. It is against these backdrop and problems that prompted the investigation into managerial practices adopted by principals' for improving teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to determine managerial practices adopted by principals' for improving teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Find out participatory decision-making practices adopted by principals for improving teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Determine teamwork practices adopted by principals for improving teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the participatory decision-making practices adopted by principals for improving teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What are the teamwork practices adopted by principals for improving teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the participatory decision-making practices adopted by principals for improving teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the teamwork practices adopted by principals for improving teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Methods

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. The study was conducted in Anambra State located in South-East geopolitical zone of Nigeria. The population of the study comprised 7,293 respondents made up of 266 principals and 7,027 teachers in the 266 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The sample for this study consisted of 809 respondents made up of 106 principals and 703 teachers drawn using proportionate stratified random sampling technique.

The researcher-developed instrument namely: 'Managerial Practices for Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (MPTJPQ) was used for data collection. The instrument had clusters A and B which were based on the two areas of managerial practices covered in the study. Cluster A had 210 items on participatory decision-making practices and cluster B contained seven items on teamwork practices. The instrument therefore contained a total of 17 items all of which are structured on a four point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D); Strongly Disagree (SD) weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The

instrument was duly validated determined by three experts who were lecturers, two from the Department of Educational Management and Policy and one in Measurement and Evaluation from the Department of Educational Foundations, all in the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. The suggestions and inputs of the experts were reflected on the final draft of the instrument. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha method which yielded coefficient values of 0.81 and 0.79 respectively with overall coefficient of 0.80.

The instrument was administered by the researcher with the help of five research assistants using direct approach. A total of 809 copies of the questionnaire were distributed and 793 copies were from teachers were properly filled and successfully retrieved, indicating 98% percent return. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and t-test to test the hypotheses. In taking decisions on the research questions, mean rating of 2.50 or above was taken as agreement, while any mean rating of below 2.50 indicate disagreement. The decision criteria for the null hypotheses is that if p-value is equal to or greater than significant value of 0.05, the null hypothesis was accepted, but if p-value is less than significant value of 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the participatory decision-making practices adopted by principals' for improving teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 1: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation Scores on the Participatory Decision-Making Practices adopted by Principals' for improving Teachers' Job Performance

S/N	ITEMS	Principals (n = 106)			Teachers (n =687)		
		\bar{x}	SD	Remark	\bar{x}	SD	Remark
1	Consult teachers during the preparation of the school time-table	2.69	1.08	Agree	2.57	1.05	Agree
2	Seek the opinions of teachers on staff affairs	2.61	1.11	Agree	2.66	1.07	Agree
3	Encourage teachers to make inputs during the preparation of school budget	2.47	0.98	Disagree	2.40	1.14	Disagree
4	Provide opportunity for teachers to make suggestions on matters regarding school community relations	2.81	1.00	Agree	2.79	1.10	Agree
5	Allow teachers to have voices on deciding safety measures for the school	2.61	1.07	Agree	2.70	1.09	Agree
6	Put the ideas of teachers in consideration in formulating school rules	2.53	1.11	Agree	2.45	1.05	Disagree
7	Involve teachers in planning co-curricular activities for students	2.71	0.91	Agree	2.75	1.06	Agree
8	Consult teachers in deciding modes of assessing students	2.89	1.01	Agree	2.90	1.04	Agree
9	Trigger teachers to share their ideas on how to carry out maintenance on school facilities	2.47	1.05	Disagree	2.41	1.03	Disagree

10	Give freedom to teachers to express their opinions on disciplinary problems	2.58	0.97	Agree	2.64	1.00	Agree
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation		2.64	1.03	Agree	2.63	1.06	Agree

Table 1 revealed that the mean ratings of both principals and teachers for items 1, 2, 4, 5, 7, 8 and 10 are above the cut off mean of 2.50 indicating agreement with the items as participatory decision-making practices applied by principals for improving the job performance of teachers. On the other hand, the mean ratings of both principals and teachers for items 3 and 9 are below the cut off mean score of 2.50 indicating disagreement with the items as participatory decision-making practices applied by principals for improving the job performance of teachers. The mean ratings of principals which is 2.53 for items 6 is above the cut off mean score of 2.50 indicating agreement with the items, while that of the teachers for the items which is 2.45 is below 2.50 indicating disagreement with the principals on the items.

The cluster standard deviation scores which stood at 1.03 and 1.06 for both principals and teachers respectively are closer to the mean indicating similarity in their responses in each cluster. The clusters means of 2.64 and 2.63 for principals and teachers respectively which are above 2.50 indicated agreement that participatory decision-making practices are adopted by principals' for improving teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 2: What are the teamwork practices adopted by principals for improving teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 2: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation Scores on the Teamwork Practices adopted by Principals' for improving Teachers' Job Performance

S/N	ITEMS	Principals (n = 106)			Teachers (n =687)		
		\bar{x}	SD	Remark	\bar{x}	SD	Remark
11	Constitute different committee to foster teamwork among teachers	2.89	1.08	Agree	2.85	1.00	Agree
12	Assign group responsibility to some teachers	2.78	1.11	Agree	2.64	1.07	Agree
13	Encourage team teaching among teachers	2.67	1.05	Agree	2.66	1.08	Agree
14	Work together with teachers to ensure coverage of scheme of work	2.44	1.00	Disagree	2.39	1.10	Disagree
15	Join force with teacher to resolve conflict in the school	2.48	1.13	Disagree	2.37	1.08	Disagree
16	Entrust the responsibility of organizing sporting activities to group of teachers to work as a team	2.72	0.94	Agree	2.81	0.93	Agree
17	Team up with teachers to develop school programmes	2.66	1.12	Agree	2.58	1.02	Agree
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation		2.66	1.06	Agree	2.61	1.04	Agree

As shown in table 2, the mean ratings of both principals and teachers for items 11, 12, 13, 16 and 17 are above the cut off mean of 2.50 indicating agreement with the items as teamwork practices applied by principals for improving the job performance of teachers. On the other

hand, the mean ratings of both principals and teachers for items 14 and 15 are below the cut off mean score of 2.50 indicating disagreement with the items as teamwork practices applied by principals for improving the job performance of teachers.

The cluster standard deviation scores which stood at 1.04 and 1.04 for both principals and teachers respectively indicated that there is homogeneity amongst their means responses which showed a similar consensus of opinion. The clusters means of 2.66 and 2.61 for principals and teachers respectively which are above 2.50 indicated agreement that teamwork practices are adopted by principals for improving teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the participatory decision-making practices adopted by principals for improving teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 3: The Summary of t-test Analysis no Significant Difference in the Mean Ratings of Principals and Teachers on the Participatory Decision-Making Practices adopted by Principals' for improving Teachers' Job Performance (n =793)

Group	N	\bar{X}	SD	p-value	Df	α	Remark
Principals	106	2.64	1.03	0.18	791	0.05	Not Significant
Teachers	687	2.63	1.06				

Table 3 revealed that the p-value of 0.18 is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the participatory decision-making practices adopted by principals for improving teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the teamwork practices adopted by principals for improving teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 4: The Summary of t-test Analysis no Significant Difference in the Mean Ratings of Principals and Teachers on the Teamwork Practices adopted by Principals for improving Teachers' Job Performance (n =793)

Group	N	\bar{X}	SD	p-value	Df	α	Remark
Principals	106	2.66	1.06	0.11	791	0.05	Not Significant
Teachers	687	2.61	1.04				

As indicated in table 4, the p-value of 0.11 is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the teamwork practices adopted by principals for improving teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Discussion

The finding of this study revealed that participatory decision-making practices are adopted by principals for improving teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This is in an agreement with the finding of Ossai and Okokoyo (2023) which

showed that principals adopted participatory decision-making strategies in public secondary schools. The participatory decision-making practices adopted by principals' for improving teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State included to consult teachers during the preparation of the school time-table, seek the opinions of teachers on staff affairs, provide opportunity for teachers to make suggestions on matters regarding school community relations, allow teachers to have voices on deciding safety measures for the school, involve teachers in planning co-curricular activities for students, consult teachers in deciding modes of assessing students and give freedom to teachers to express their opinions on disciplinary problems. The principals adopted participatory decision-making practices to probably encourage free-flow of ideas that lead to innovative solutions to problems of public secondary schools. Teachers who make contributions on school affairs as result of participatory decision-making practices of principals feel genuinely valued and thereby reciprocate by implementing the final decisions made in secondary schools. It was also found that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the participatory decision-making practices adopted by principals for improving teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This is in line with the finding of Wakili, Unung and Ukpata (2019) which indicated that there is no significant difference in the mean scores of principals and teachers on the decision-making practices of principals for teachers' job performance in secondary schools. This also supported the finding of Ossai and Okokoyo (2023) which indicated that there was no significant difference between principals and teachers on the strategies adopted by principals in decision-making process in public secondary schools. The agreement with the findings could be attributed to the similarity in educational level, participants and time span of the study. Participatory decision-making practices strengthen the sense of belongingness among teachers which motivate them to improve their job performance in public secondary schools.

The result of the study showed that teamwork practices are adopted by principals for improving teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This is contrary to the finding of Ayeni and Fakunle (2022) which showed that there was moderate level to which teachers perceive the use of teamwork strategies in secondary schools. The difference in geographical location could contribute to the disagreement with the finding. The teamwork practices adopted by principals' for improving teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State were to constitute different committee to foster teamwork among teachers, assign group responsibility to some teachers, encourage team teaching among teachers, entrust the responsibility of organizing sporting activities to group of teachers to work as a team and team up with teachers to develop school programmes. Teamwork practices are possibly adopted by principals to encourage diverse perspectives to solving problems and improve the job performance of teachers in secondary schools in Anambra State. Teamwork practices of principals provide opportunity for teachers to improve their skills and enrich knowledge for effective execution of their duties in secondary schools. Further result indicated that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the teamwork practices adopted by principals for improving teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This agreed with the finding of Amadi (2019) which revealed that principals and teachers of public senior secondary schools did not significantly differ in their mean rating of teamwork. The agreement in finding could be attributed to similarity in participants which are principals and teachers in secondary schools within the same country. Teamwork practices of principals cultivate strong relationships and build favourable atmosphere that can make teacher comfortable in performing their job to achieve common goals of secondary education.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it is concluded that principals adopt managerial practices for improving teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Managerial practices of participatory decision-making and teamwork are probably adopted by principals to build cohesion and encourage exchange of innovative ideas to improve the job performance of teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Managerial practices adopted by principals tend to contribute to success recorded by teachers and students in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

1. Principals should undertake leadership courses to augment the skills and knowledge of participatory decision-making practices for improving the job performance of teachers.
2. Anambra State Ministry of Education should develop policy, set standards and engage in regular supervision of activities of secondary schools to strengthen the teamwork practices of principals for improving the job performance of teachers.

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